

Impact of Gestational and Pre-Gestational Diabetes Mellitus on the Foetal Heart

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ABSTRACT

Foetal cardiac structural and functional features have been examined in pregnancies diabetic and non-diabetic and healthy pregnancies. During 15.1.17-15.7.17, cardiac structure and function assessment was scheduled of 50 healthy pregnant women, 25 pregnant women with gestational diabetes and 25 with pre-gestational diabetes. The thickness of foetal interventricular septum (IVS) was significantly more in diabetic group as compared to non-diabetics ($p < 0.05$) but no one was having an IVS > 2 SD from normal. The top velocity of tricuspid E and the ratio of E/A was considerably low in diabetic group ($p < 0.05$). Values of tricuspid valve Ea and the ratio of Ea/Aa were less in the diabetic group as compared to control group ($p < 0.05$) but there was no considerable difference in between pre-gestational diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes mellitus ($p > 0.05$). In diabetic pregnancies the most common structural abnormality is the interventricular septal hypertrophy. No risk is linked to foetal with these changes unless it results in the functional impairment. Therefore, it is believed that it is necessary to monitor the diabetic pregnant women for foetal cardiac diastolic dysfunction.

Keywords : Gestational Diabetes, Pre-Gestational Diabetes

INTRODUCTION

1% to 2% complications to all pregnancies are caused by diabetes mellitus. It has increased prenatal morbidities and risk of mortality although the prevalence is relatively low. Maternal diabetes mellitus enhances five-fold perinatal morbidities and mortality than the normal pregnancies. Babies 5% to 8% of diabetic mothers have been seen with prominent congenital problem. Development of cardiovascular system gets particularly influenced from hyperglycaemia. Congenital heart issue found in the diabetic mothers' babies suggest that the rising of defects may be from teratogenic effect in the initial stage of development of heart (Corrigan et al. 2009).

Insulin binding cell receptors control the growth of foetal. Foetal hyperinsulinemia results in hypertrophy and hyperplasia in myocardial cells by way of enhancing myocardial glycogen, protein

and fat mix in foetal heart due to interventricular septum (IVS) especially very high in the receptors. Babies who are affected have hypertrophic septum and occasionally hypertrophic left and right ventricle walls. Mass of cardiac muscle increases because of foetal hyperinsulinemia and this rise is not found connected with weight of baby at the time of birth. On the histopathological examination of myocardial cell inflammatory cell infiltration, disorganisation and glycogen deposition in cellular cytoplasm are not seen; although, hydropic changes exist (Ren et al. 2011). The amount of cardiac involvement is connected with the foeto-neonatal hyperinsulinemia and maternal diabetes. Researchers have revealed that during pregnancy diabetes of all types have negative effect on heart.

Mainly, asymmetric septal hypertrophy, obstruction of ventricle outflow and thickening of ventricular wall may be found on examination of echocardiographic. There is also increase of prevalence of other congenital heart illness. It has been revealed in the studies that ventricular septal defects and atrial septal defects, pulmonary atresia, double outlet right ventricles, transposition of the great arteries, the tetralogy of Fallot and foetal cardio-myopathy, mitral atresia and cardio-myopathy (which starts with diastolic dysfunction and may lead to systolic dysfunction and failure of heart) may be found (Miyake 2001; Abu-Sulaiman and Subaih 2004; Russell et al. 2008; Lisowski et al. 2010). The object of the current research is to compare the functional and structural properties of foetal hearts between healthy and diabetic pregnancies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patient population

During January 2017 to July 2017, 50 healthy pregnant women, 25 pregnant women with gestational diabetes and 25 with pre-gestational diabetes women were made part of the study who was visiting the outpatient clinic of Paediatric Cardiology Department, Combined Military

Hospital, Lahore. Information was given to all participants and an informed written consent was obtained from them. Foetal age in the pregnant women was determined by the obstetric ultrasound measurements. Criteria for exclusion was renal diseases, diabetic vasculopathy, maternal hypertension, connective tissue diseases, foetal congenital anomalies, uncertainty regarding the last menstrual period, multiple pregnancies, intrauterine growth retardation, and pregnancy with poorly controlled diabetes (HbA1c level >6.5%). Selection of pregnant women having pre-gestational diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes mellitus as per their medical history. The group with high risk had age >35 years, positive family history, gestational diabetes in a previous pregnancy, glycosuria, obesity or pregnancies with unexplained stillbirth and macrosomic babies (> 4000 g). A 75 g Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) was carried during the first prenatal visit. It was repeated at 28 weeks of gestation when the result was negative. The 75 g OGTT was passed by 28 low-risk pregnant women.

Abnormal values of two or more is the presence of gestational diabetes mellitus (fasting glucose > 95 mg/dL, 1 h > 180 mg/dL, 2 h > 155 mg/dL) were accepted. In the presence of the following features the diabetes mellitus was diagnosed; fasting plasma glucose level > 126 mg/dL, plasma glucose > 200 mg/dL 2 h after a 75-g oral glucose load (as in a glucose-tolerance test), symptoms of hyperglycaemia and casual plasma glucose > 200 mg/dL or glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) level > 6.5 mg/dL.

Foetal echocardiography

Philips IE33 ultrasound system (Philips, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) with 3.5 and 5.1 MHz transducers was used for performing foetal echocardiogram. The data of doppler was assessed under 30 angle and recorded. All the pregnant women had undergone 3 separate assessment and they used the average. Patient's diabetic status was not informed to the practitioner. For recording of foetal parameters, inclusive of head circumference, abdominal circumference, biparietal diameter, and femur length, a systematic two-dimensional foetal echocardiography scan was done. The measurement of tricuspid valve annulus values, mitral, pulmonary, aortic and Cardiothoracic index was performed. M-mode echocardiography was used for measuring the ventricular end diastolic and end systolic diameters. The IVS and the posterior wall thickness immediately below the atrioventricular valves the M-line was kept perpendicular to the interventricular septum. For

the purpose of diagnosing thickening of IVS, the thickness of an interventricular septal of > 2 SD for gestational age at diastolic was applied. The calculations of shortening fraction (EDD-EDD)/EDD and RV and LV systolic ejection was made. There was recording of Mitral and tricuspid inflow velocities with a pulsed-wave Dopplera late diastolic peak flow velocity (A) and early diastolic peak flow velocity (E). The pulmonary artery peak systolic velocity evaluation was performed on a short axis view was applied and the aortic peak systolic velocity evaluation was performed on an apical 5 chamber view was applied. Immediate below the semilunar valves the Doppler cursor was placed. The apical 4 chamber view was used for evaluation of Tissue Doppler. They achieved Doppler angle of <10. There was recording of value of both the atrioventricular valve annulus of the systolic flow velocity [Sa: Early systolic peak flow velocity/late diastolic peak flow velocity] and the Ea (early diastolic peak flow velocity with tissue Doppler) and Aa (late diastolic peak flow velocity with tissue Doppler). The Atrioventricular valve to Ea/Aa ratio was evaluated.

Statistical analysis

SPSS software (ver. 22; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL) was used for the statistical analysis. Reporting of data was as means $\pm$ SD. One-way ANOVA was used for comparing the 3 groups after that HSD post hoc test of Tukey for the determination of the group prominently different from one another. In order to indicate statistical significance p value < 0.05 was considered.

RESULTS

Overall the analysis was made over 50 healthy and 50 diabetic pregnant women. The performing of foetal echocardiography was at mean gestational age of 31.3 ± 1.2 weeks in the GDM group, at age of 33.1 ± 0.5 weeks in the pre-GDM group and at age of 34.2 ± 1.1 weeks in the control group. The division of pregnant women was made into 3 groups: in group 1 there were 25 pre-gestational diabetic pregnant women in group 2 there were 25 gestational diabetic pregnant women and in group 3 there were 25 non-diabetic pregnant women. 20 women from group 1 were getting insulin and 5 women were getting diet therapy. 20 women from group 2 were getting insulin and the rest 5 were getting diet therapy.

There was no detection of statistically significant difference in the above-mentioned group with respect to quantitative variables like age, parity, gravida, gestational age at ultrasonography, sonography foetal biometry, birth weight (g) and

Apgar score at 15 min. Diabetic pregnant women give earlier birth. The group with diabetes was categorised by BMI, HbA1c (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Characteristics	Pre-gestational DM (n=25)	Gestational DM (n=25)	Control (n=25)	p-value
Maternal age (years), mean (SD)	30.25 ± 3.5	28.44 ± 5.3	29.33 ± 4.4	.23
Gravida (number)	2.4 ± 1.4	2.3 ± 1.3	2.2 ± 1.4	.18
Parity (number)	1.4 ± 1.1	1.3 ± 1.2	1.3 ± 1.1	.34
Biparietal diameter (weeks)	32.3 ± 2.3	33.1 ± 2.2	32.4 ± 2.1	.22
Abdominal circumference (weeks)	33.2 ± 3.1	34.1 ± 2.8	33.2 ± 3.0	.41
Femur length (weeks)	32.4 ± 1.4	33.1 ± 1.3	31.2 ± 1.3	.14
Gestational age at ultrasonographic MPI evaluation (weeks)	33.1 ± 0.5	31.3 ± 1.2	34.2 ± 1.1	.25
Gestational age at delivery	34.1 ± 1.3	33.1 ± 1.1	32.3 ± 1.2	.33
Hemoglobin A1c, mean (SD)	4.22 ± 1.1	4.12 ± 0.5	3.55 ± 1.4	.001
Birthweight (g), mean (SD)	3453 ± 343	3532 ± 433	3342 ± 522	.44
Body mass index	29.4 ± 4.3	32.3 ± 5.1	27.4 ± 4.1	.001
Apgar at 5 min	9.1 ± 0.4	9.3 ± 0.3	9.1 ± 0.4	.23

The interventricular septum was considerably thicker in the group with pre-gestational diabetes (4 ± 2.1 mm) against gestational diabetes (3.20 ± 0.1 mm) and control (3.08 ± 1.2 mm) groups ($p < 0.05$). However, foetus interventricular septum thickness was not more than 2 SDs over the mean. No significant statistical difference was found among the 3 groups in right and left ventricular wall thickness, functional shortening or ejection. In the group with diabetes (pre-gestational diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes mellitus groups) the tricuspid E/A diastolic index and E velocity was prominently low as compared to control group ($p < 0.05$) and in the three groups there was absence of any difference in the A velocity. No significant difference was found in the diabetic groups in the tricuspid E E/A diastolic index or A velocity. Also there was found no difference in the mitral valve E/A diastolic index A and E velocities. There was no significant difference in the three groups with regard to pulmonary valve peak flow velocity at pulsed-wave Doppler examination of aortic. The value of Tissue Doppler examination of tricuspid valve Ea and ratio of Ea/Aa were low in group with diabetes (pre-gestational diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes mellitus groups) as compared to control group ($p < 0.05$), but no significant difference was present in gestational diabetes mellitus and pre-gestational diabetes mellitus groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference present in the three groups with regard to AV valves and calculated Sa values ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Insulin at increased level results in foetal heart muscle hypertrophy. The diabetic mothers' foetuses are at risk of changes of myocardial hypertrophic because of foetal hyperinsulinism and

hyperglycaemia. Particularly this can result in ventricular outflow tract obstruction and asymmetric interventricular septal hypertrophy. It has been reported by Fouda et al (2013) that ainterventricular septum is thick in the foetuses of gestational diabetes mothers than in healthy pregnant women. In their researches the interventricular septum was found in 21% pre-gestational diabetes mellitus and 10% gestational diabetes mellitus. Groups having septal hypertrophy have significantly high HbA1c as compared to the groups without septal hypertrophy. Nevertheless, there was 9 foetuses with maternal septal hypertrophy having normal HbA1c, which has been elaborated with reference to hypo- and hyperglycaemic periods (Fouda et al. 2013). It has been found by Chu et al. that thickness of interventricular septum was quite high in the groups with diabetes. The distinction was made in between well and poorly controlled diabetes mellitus groups and found no difference in the groups with respect to the thickness of IVS. However, in the well-controlled group the left ventricular posterior wall was thick as compared to poorly controlled group (Chu et al. 2012). In a prospective case-control study of foetal hearts diabetic and non-diabetic it has been found by Flores that though normal in structure but foetal hearts with diabetes had a thick septum in foetus than in normal pregnancies, Functional abnormalities not yet determined were seen in the both the groups (Flores et al. 2011). However, no difference had been found by Wong et al. (2003) in interventricular septum or thickness of posterior wall in between poorly and well controlled groups with diabetes but their research included only 20 pregnant women with diabetes.

It has been shown by Sardesai et al. (2001) that though the reason for foetal diastolic dysfunction was diabetes, but obviously it is independent of interventricular septum hypertrophy. In this population, the thickness of IVS was prominently more in group with diabetes as compared to the control group but none of the participant was having IVS over 2 SD beyond the mean. In fact, the thickness of IVS was akin between the pregnancies with or without diabetes. Besides the septum thickness, the mean HbA1c values were also more in the group with diabetes as compared to control group. No other significant difference was found in ventricular diameters or thickness of wall. It has been revealed by some reports that changes of intrauterine myocardial hypertrophic decrease the contraction and relaxation and further deteriorate the ventricular diastolic function. This scenario has been construed as pointer of myocardial insufficiency. However, myocardial function effect on overall myocardial hypertrophy is disputed (Prefumo et al. 2005), diabetes is considered a reason for cardiac functional and structural changes. These may be the initial symptoms of diastolic dysfunction in cardiomyopathy diabetes which can result in symptomatic heart failure and progressive systolic dysfunction. In a study conducted by Ren et al. (2011) in 92 cases, pulmonary velocities and aortic were considerably more than the control group, that fact may elaborate the difference in arterial blood pressure, ventricular contraction force and cardiac output.

44 gestational pregnant women with diabetes were assessed in the 3rd trimester by Chu et al. They found high pulmonary velocity and aortic than in the control group during first 2 trimesters, but during the last trimester they did not detect any difference in the groups (Chu et al. 2012). In the current research, the evaluation of the pregnant women was made in the last trimester; and pregnant women were not included who had poor glycaemic control or hypertension. Therefore, maternal hyperglycaemia and arterial blood pressure difference have been removed that may affect the results. No significant difference has been found in these groups with respect to pulmonary valve velocity or aortic. During pregnancy, septal thickness and foetal cardiac wall pointed out by E, E/a and Ea/Aa ratios, enhanced gradually and reached top level during 36 and 40 weeks. It has been shown in the studies that ventricular compliance is reduced by the myocardial hypertrophy, like right ventricular diastolic dysfunction grows in the initial period. during the life of foetal, the right ventricle has high

sensitivity for after loading changes as compared to left ventricle. Therefore, in pregnancies with diabetes, the ratio of tricuspid E/A is low as compared to the ratio of mitral E/A (Rychik 2004; Watanabe et al. 2009). Placental vascular resistance also increases by diabetes and induce right ventricular diastolic dysfunction (Aoki et al. 2004; Madazli et al. 2008). While studying values of mitral E, no difference has been shown by the E/A ratio between the 3 trimester whereas the E/A ratio and tricuspid valve E value were significantly low in a group with diabetes as compared to control group (Chu et al. 2012). In other research, no significant difference was found in control and diabetic group (Fouda et al. 2013). In another study having alike outcome, the ratio of the tricuspid valve E/A was low whereas no case of tricuspid regurgitation or with a pathological diastolic E/A index was found (Wong et al. 2007). In the current research, ratio of the tricuspid valve E/a in the group of diabetes was low as compared to control group but there was no case with respect to pathological range. No significant difference in the groups with regard to mitral valve measurement.

Moreover, no significant difference was found with respect to measurements of tricuspid valve between pre-gestational and gestational groups. Diastolic function's Tissue Doppler Imaging assessment was placed in comparison with the index Ea/Aa ratio, it is very beneficial as it comparatively gets less affected as compared with the cardiac load and heart rate (Huhta et al. 2003). In the current research, the ratio of Ea/Aa was low in group with diabetes as compared to control group, but no significant difference was found between the groups of GDM and Pre-GDM. In the life of foetal, the right ventricular diastolic dysfunction was predominant, as it has been evaluated by the tricuspid valve velocity at initial stage. The development of ventricular hypertrophy in pregnancy with diabetes and diastolic filling change compliance may get affected. It has been shown by Tan et al. (2005) that the foetal diastolic function did get affected by the diabetes, but the current research is also consistent with other recent publications.

CONCLUSION

Diabetes can be the reason for the foetal cardiac functional and structural changes. Interventricular septal hypertrophy is the most common structural change. The change is not in nature of alarming risk unless it results in functional impairment. However, worsening of foetal cardiac diastolic function can occur because of diabetes. Therefore, it is believed that it is imperative to check the

pregnant women with diabetes for foetal cardiac diastolic dysfunction. Studies based on large population are needed to set up the complete risk of

congenital heart defect in the women having diabetic pre-gestational and the benefit of routine screening.

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